

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

AN OVERVIEW OF CATARACT ACTIVITY AND THEIR SCREENING METHODS

Veeram Anjali*, G. Sindhu, C.Girish, K.Mounika

S.V.U. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, S.V. University, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 08/12/2017

Available online

31/01/2018

Keywords

Anti-Cataract Activity,
Screening Models,
Diabetes.

ABSTRACT

A cataract is a clouding of the lens in the eyes which leads to a decrease in vision. Cataracts often develop slowly and can affect one or both eyes. Cataracts are the cause of half of the blindness and 33% of visual impairment worldwide. Cataract is a multifactorial disease associated with several risk factors such as aging, diabetes, malnutrition, diarrhoea, poverty, sunlight, smoking, hypertension and renal failure. Various convenient models are available for the evaluation of drugs for the prevention of cataract formation they are galactose induced cataracts in rats, naphthalene induced cataracts in rats, selenite induced cataract in rats etc. Various medicinal plants having anti-cataract activity were reported with minimal adverse effects. Even there is the need to find out novel drug with minimal adverse effects to treat the cataract activity and to prevent the blindness in humans.

Corresponding author

Veeram Anjali

S.V.U Womens Hostel,

Premises – 2, S.V. University, Tirupathi,

Room No: 708, Pin Code: 517502.

9494304835,

anjali.ammulu46@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Veeram Anjali et al.** An Overview of Cataract Activity and Their Screening Methods. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(01).

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INTRODUCTION

CATARACT DEFINITION:

Cataract, the clouding of the lens develops later in the life and it is most likely the consequence of decades of accumulated damage to long lived lens protein. It is the most common cause of blindness. Visual loss occurs because of opacification of the lens obstructs light from passing and being focused onto the retina¹⁻³.

The cataract formation involves the wide range of mechanisms for some instances the oxidative mechanism also plays an important role in biological phenomena, including cataract formation. The formation of superoxide radicals in the aqueous humor and in lens, lens and its derivatization to other potent oxidants may be responsible for initiating various toxic biochemical reactions leading to opacification. The aldose reductase enzyme also plays an important role in pathogenesis of cataract. The aldose reductase acts on glucose, galactose and xylose and convert them into their respective alcohols. These alcohols, also known as polyols accumulate within the lens there by producing osmotic effects. Since polyols are not capable of diffusing out easily nor metabolizes rapidly and causes hyper tonicity responsible for opacification.

FIGURE NO 1: The figure describes about the opacification of lens in cataract formation. The above figure shows the difference between the normal eye and the cataract formed eye.

CAUSES OF CATARACT:

Various factors that leads to the formation of cataract are

- Diabetes
- Oxidation of lens
- Dehydration
- Daylight
- Diet
- Lipid peroxidation

These factors attributes to the generation of the lens opacification in elderly persons. Other risk factors that leads to the opacification of the lens includes

- Smoking
- Environmental factors
- Lack of consumption of antioxidants
- Nutritional deficiency etc.,

The above factor also increases the risk of development of cataract²⁰. During hyperglycemia extracellular glucose diffuses into the lens leads to the post- translational modifications.

Prevalence and Incidence

Several previous reports give details about the prevalence and incidence of cataract worldwide. “Prevalence” is the total number of people having cataract in a population at a given time.

While, “Incidence” means the number of new cases that occur over a given period of time. A very high incidence of cataract has been noted by Minassian and Mehra. They have correlated the incidence of cataract with age. There was a steep rise in cataract incidence after the age of fifty.

Cataract General Mechanism:

The extreme opacification affects the transparent nature of lens. Lens transparency is necessary to enter incoming light passes through lens and falls on retina to form image. Opacification of lens causes light scattering, as light passes through lens and then to the retina where diminished focus of light impairs vision. The visual acuity is lost in cataract due to the absorption of light by less transparent lens. The generalized mechanism of cataract includes lens fibre cells disruption, cellular protein aggregation and lens cell cytoplasm dysfunctioning.

EVALUATION OF DRUGS FOR THE PREVENTION OF CATARACT FORMATION:

Diabetic patients are known to have a higher incidence of cataract formation which produces changes in the transparency or the refractory index of the lens. The involvement of polyol metabolism and role of the enzyme aldose reductase is now well established in the genesis of diabetic cataracts⁴⁻⁷. Aldose reductase catalyses the reduction of aldoses like glucose and galactose to corresponding polyols which do not readily diffuse through intact cellular membranes and create severe osmotic stress within the lenticular cells leading to cellular swelling and loss of integrity of the cellular membrane⁸.

Thus sugar induced cataractogenesis has been directly associated with polyol accumulation. Aldose reductase inhibitors have been shown to prevent sugar induced cataract formation⁹⁻¹⁰.

GALACTOSE INDUCED CATARACTS IN RATS:**ANIMAL:**

Wistar Albino rats.

- Young wistar albino rats of either sex weighing between 50-60g are used.
- Incidence of cataract formation is studied according to the method described by Dvornik et al (1973)¹² and partially modified by Parmar and Ghosh (1979)¹³.
- The control animals were fed on a diet consisting of 30g/100g of galactose with the following composition:
 1. Galactose: 30.0g
 2. Maize starch: 40.0g
 3. Dried powdered milk: 15.0g
 4. Sodium chloride: 1.5g
 5. Calcium phosphate: 2.0g
 6. Potassium sulphate: 1.0g
 7. Ferrous sulphate: 0.5g
 8. Codliver oil: 2.0g
 9. Saturated vegetable oil: 8.0g
 10. Vitamin B1, B2, B16, B12 and C: in traces.
- The other group receives a similar diet mixed with an aldose reductase inhibitor which replaces an equivalent amount of maize starch.
- The eyes of each animal were examined daily and a clear opacity formed in any of the eye was taken as an evidence of cataract formation.
- In the control rats a few scattered vacuoles are seen from fourth and fifth day onwards and the cataracts in the form of nuclear opacity started appearing from the 12th day onwards after the commencement of galactosemic diet.

NAPHTHALENE INDUCED CATARACT IN RATS:

Systemic administration of naphthalene has been shown to induce cataracts in Brown- Norway rats and SPF C57 b1/6 mice, which can be used for the evaluation of aldose reductase inhibitors¹⁴.

METHODOLOGY:**ANIMAL:**

Brown- Norway rats.

- Six weeks old female Brown- Norway rats weighing about 80- 100g are used.
- They are maintained on standard laboratory chow diet and water ad libitum.
- Naphthalene is dissolved in warm paraffin oil in a concentration of 10g/ 100 ml and administered orally in a dose of 1g/kg every second day for 6 weeks.
- Test compound may be administered orally every day or applied as eye drops 1-4 times daily.
- Slit lamp microscopy following mydriasis produced by 1% atropine is performed before starting the treatment and thereafter every week till the animals are sacrificed.
- Scheimpflug photography of the anterior eye segment is carried out before starting the treatment, after 3 weeks of treatment and before the animals is sacrificed.
- Before sacrificing the animal blood sample through cardiac puncture under ether anesthesia are taken.
- After sacrifice, the fresh weights of lenses levels of oxidized and reduced glutathione and concentration of test compound in the lenses and in blood samples are determined.
- The values of treated animals are compared with those of controls.
- This method has been suitably modified for rapid induction of cataracts in SPFC 57 bI/8 mice.
- These mice are treated with Phenobarbitol for inducing cytochrome P-450 and then administered naphthalene by intraperitoneal route¹⁵.

SELENITE INDUCED CATARACT IN RATS:

Sodium selenite has been successfully used for the induction of cataracts in young rats¹⁶.

METHODOLOGY:**ANIMAL:**

Male Wistar rat

- Male Wistar rat are used. On the second day of life, the suckling rats are divided in such a way that 8 males are housed with one mother.
- On the 10th day of life when they are absolutely dependent on the mother for their nutrition, a single dose of 0.02 μ M solution of sodium selenite($\text{Na}_2\text{Se O}_3$) is administered subcutaneously to 3 experimental groups receiving 10, 20, and 40 μ M/kg of selenite respectively.
- The control group receives 60 μ M/kg of Na_2SO_3 a sulphur compound homologous with selenite.
- Mothers of sucklings are maintained on standard laboratory chow diet with water ad libitum.
- All the animals are examined daily for 20 days and there after the experiments are terminated.
- Cataracts in the sucklings are visible to the naked eye after they open their eyes on 15th or 16th day of life.
- The opacity appears yellowish white and is localized in the center of the lense, hence called the nuclear cataracts in adult animals.
- Experimental cataracts have also been reported after treatment with acetaminophen¹⁷ and induction of cytochrome P-450 in C57 BL/6 mice, x- irradiation¹⁸ and corticosteroids¹⁹ in Brown- Norway rats.

FIGURE NO 2: The above figure shows the formation of cataract in the pupil region. The figure explains the formation of a blurry image when the lens is opacified by the formation of cataract.

TABLE NO: 1. PLANTS WITH ANTI- CATARACT ACTIVITY.

S.NO	PLANTS WITH CATARACT ACTIVITY	PLANT PART USED
1.	Adhatoda vasica	Whole plant
2.	Allium cepa	Whole plant
3.	Cassia fistula	Whole plant
4.	Angelica dahurica	Whole plant
5.	Citrus aurantium	Whole plant
6.	Cochlospermum religiosum	Whole plant
7.	Emilia sonchifolia	Whole plant
8.	Erigeron annuus	Whole plant
9.	Ginko biloba	Whole plant
10.	Momordica charantia	Whole plant
11.	Moringa olifera	Whole plant
12.	Ocimum santum	Whole plant
13.	Origanum vulgare	Whole plant
14.	Pterocarpus Marsupium	Whole plant
15.	Silybum Mrianum	Whole plant
16.	Trigonella foenum graceum	Whole plant
17.	Vitex negundo	Whole plant
18.	Withinia somnifera	Whole plant
19.	Curcuma longa	Whole plant
20.	Syzygium cumini	Whole plant

The above table gives information about the plants having cataract activity and the plant parts used to prove anti-cataract activity.

CONCLUSION

Cataract is a multifactorial disease associated with several risk factors such as aging, diabetes, malnutrition, diarrhoea, poverty, sunlight, smoking, hypertension and renal failure. Free radical induced oxidative stress is postulated to be perhaps the major factor leading to experimental cataract formation. This hypothesis is supported by the anti-cataractogenic effect of various nutritional physiological antioxidants in experimental animals.

Various convenient models are available to study cataract in experimental animals viz. selenite cataract, galactose cataract, steroid cataract and UV-radiations induced cataract. The morphological and biochemical characteristics of this model have been extensively investigated; moreover, these models show a number of general similarities to human cataract. The reliability and extensive characterization of these models makes them useful tools for rapid screening of potential anti cataract agents. Various natural and synthetic compounds of differing chemical structures have been reported to prevent experimental cataract *in vitro* as well as *in vivo* by virtue of antioxidant, calpain activation, lens aldose reductase inhibition, anti-glycation and lens calcium concentration inhibition properties. There is a need to evaluate additional compounds for their anti cataract efficacy attributed to more than one mechanism of action to mitigate the problem of lens opacification.

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